

Examination of University Students' Tendencies to Violence and Holiganism in Sports

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Abstract

In this study, it was aimed to examine the violence and hooliganism tendencies of university students in sports. In the study, 290 university students who continue their education at Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Physical Education and Sports High School participated. In order to determine the distribution of personal information of the participants participating in the study, the "personal information form" created by the researchers was used. There are 9 questions in the form such as gender, age, and the team they support. In order to get the opinions of the participants on the causes of violence in sports, Reyhan et al. (2020) "Basics of violence in sports" scale was used. In the study, the data were analyzed with the SPSS 26 package program for Windows. First, the internal consistency coefficient was calculated for the data collection tool ($\alpha=.809$; $N=25$). The distribution of the data was determined by examining the kurtosis and skewness values. In addition to descriptive statistical methods, one-way analysis of variance test, Pearson correlation analysis and independent sample t-test were used in the study. With the results obtained from the survey data; While significant differences were observed in the parameters of the participants' age, gender and being a member of any fan group, there was no significant difference in the parameters of smoking, alcohol use, licensed sports and the frequency of going to the match. In addition, when the survey results are examined, the highest average score obtained by the participants from the scale of the basics of violence in sports is in the "violence caused by referee decisions" sub-dimensions, "violence caused by the media", "violence caused by fans and cheerleaders" and "violence caused by coaches and soccer coaches" was found to be sequential. As a result, when the Violence and Holiganism Tendencies of University Students in Sports are examined; It was seen that male students got higher scores than females. In addition, it was seen that the participants tended to violence mostly due to referee decisions and media.

Keywords: Football, Hooliganism, Violence.

Üniversite öğrencilerinin sporda şiddet ve holiganizm eğilimlerinin incelenmesi

Özet

Bu çalışmada üniversite öğrencilerinin sporda şiddet ve holiganizm eğilimlerinin incelenmesi amaçlanmıştır. Çalışmaya Hatay Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Yüksek Okulu'nda öğrenimine devam eden 290 üniversite öğrencisi katılmıştır. Çalışmaya katılan katılımcıların kişisel bilgilerinin dağılımını belirlemek amacıyla araştırmacılar tarafından oluşturulan "kişisel bilgi formu" kullanılmıştır. Formda cinsiyet, yaş, tuttukları takım gibi 9 soru bulunmaktadır. Katılımcıların sporda şiddetin nedenlerine ilişkin görüşlerini almak için Reyhan ve arkadaşlarının (2020) "Sporda şiddetin temelleri" ölçeği kullanılmıştır. Araştırmada veriler Windows için SPSS 26 paket programı ile analiz edilmiştir. İlk olarak veri toplama aracı için iç tutarlılık katsayısı hesaplanmıştır ($\alpha=.809$; $N=25$). Verilerin dağılımı basıklık ve çarpıklık değerleri incelenerek belirlenmiştir. Çalışmada tanımlayıcı istatistiksel yöntemlerin yanı sıra tek yönlü varyans analizi testi, Pearson korelasyon analizi ve bağımsız örneklem t-testi kullanılmıştır. Anket verilerinden elde edilen sonuçlarla; katılımcıların yaş, cinsiyet ve herhangi bir taraftar grubuna üye olma parametrelerinde anlamlı farklılıklar gözlemlenirken, sigara, alkol kullanımı, lisanslı spor yapma ve maça gitme sıklığı parametrelerinde anlamlı bir farklılığa rastlanmamıştır. Ayrıca anket sonuçları incelendiğinde katılımcıların sporda şiddetin temelleri ölçeğinden aldıkları en yüksek puan ortalamasının "hakem kararlarından kaynaklanan şiddet" alt boyutunda olduğu, "medyadan kaynaklanan şiddet", "taraftar ve amigolardan kaynaklanan şiddet" ve "antrenör ve futbolcu çalıştırmacılarından kaynaklanan şiddet" alt boyutlarının ise sıralı olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Sonuç olarak Üniversite Öğrencilerinin Sporda Şiddet ve Holiganizm Eğilimleri incelendiğinde; erkek öğrencilerin kadınlara göre daha yüksek puanlar aldığı görülmüştür. Ayrıca katılımcıların en çok hakem kararları ve medya nedeniyle şiddet eğiliminde oldukları görülmüştür.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Futbol, Holiganizm, Şiddet.

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Introduction

In today's world, sports organizations have reached an international audience and reached a large audience and started to become an industry that provides large economic revenues (Yüksel, et al., 2023). Sports organizations, which have started to become an industry, include many people both in sports and in the production and consumption phases. This industry, which directly targets multiple audiences, changes people's perspective on sports and affects expectations from the results of sports competitions (Özen, et al., 2013). Football, one of the team sports that is a part of this globalized industry, has a great importance in this structuring. Stadiums, which are the areas where football exhibits its performances in this global industry, have become the most popular places to learn about mass psychology by bringing together a large number of spectators (Üstünel & Alkurt, 2015). As a result of the reach and globalization of sports, competitions have become a global phenomenon that has started to strengthen relations between countries, support global peace and revitalize cultural interactions (Sancar, 2012 cited in Çakto & Altınok, 2020). Sports, which is usually brought to the agenda with violent incidents in the world, is an important factor that supports the development of social awareness and social health conditions by developing an environment of love and peace. At the same time, besides positive situations such as the employment of individuals in the society and the entertaining effect of the society, there are also negative effects such as the difficulties faced by people such as health personnel, security guards and the decrease in the interest of the audience in case of violent incidents (Ibid). The football branch, which is constantly gaining value, growing and developing with the advancing times, not only improves the working areas of the athletes, but also increases the level of satisfaction by providing better conditions for the spectators. However, football is a sport branch that can be played by many individuals without the distinction of amateur or professional without the expectation of professional or financial gain. Although football played at amateur level is preferred as an entertaining sport that people prefer for a healthy life, football preferred to be played professionally is applied in the form of athletes participating in the competition in front of the audience or in the consciousness of the competition to win. In this case, the fact that the spectators enjoy the football played and come to watch it has a serious importance in terms of the revenues obtained from the audience. Revenues from stadium viewership rates, which are generated by the interest of spectators in professional teams, rank at the top as a very large revenue item. For these reasons, professional club managers try to get their share of this audience revenue market by putting forward attitudes and actions in order to encourage the audience to watch the match. Apart from all these situations, fan groups are also integrated with the team they support, and in case of success or failure, it seriously affects the happiness and unhappiness of the fans. In fact, these situations

are carried even further and fanatical fans hate the people and institutions they hold responsible for failure and as a result, they may resort to violence (Acet, 2005). Aggression and violence in football can occur sometimes among fans and sometimes among the players themselves. The main starting points of these violent incidents may vary. The reasons such as the athletes playing harder than they should, playing incorrectly, the attitudes or negative behaviors of the spectators, the wrong decisions of the referee, the unfortunate statements of the managers, the provocative cheers of the stadium cheerleaders and the provocative news of the media prepare the environment for the occurrence of violence and aggression in football (Demirel, 2013). When the literature is examined, it is seen that many studies have been conducted on violence and hooliganism in sports. However, in most of the studies, it has been seen that violence and hooliganism in sports are handled separately. In addition, it has been seen that the opinions of the fans are generally discussed in the studies. In this context, it is thought that this study will contribute to examining the violence and hooliganism tendencies of university students, determining the factors that cause violence and hooliganism and producing solutions for prevention.

METHODS

Research Model

In this study, violence and hooliganism tendencies of university students in sports were examined. Quantitative (numerical) method was used in the research and the survey model technique was used among quantitative research techniques. The survey model is an approach that aims to describe a situation that has been experienced in the past or still exists as it is. The subject event, individual or object is tried to be defined as it is in its own conditions and without any intervention (Karasar, 2013).

Study Group

A total of 290 university students attending Mustafa Kemal University School of Physical Education and Sports participated in the study. Participants were determined according to the simple random sampling method. It is a systematized version of simple random sampling method. It can be applied when the universe is large, homogeneous and the unit list is readily available. The units to be selected for the sample are selected from the list at equal intervals. The sampling interval is obtained by dividing the number of units in the universe (N) by the sample size (n) (N/n).

Data Collection

In order to collect the data in the study, firstly, the written permission of the authors who developed the scale used was obtained. Then, ethics committee approval was obtained from Mustafa Kemal University Social and Human Sciences Ethics Committee. With the ethical approval, permission was obtained from Mustafa Kemal University School of Physical Education and Sports to collect data and the data were collected online from the participants via Google Forms. Participation was voluntary and participants had to approve the voluntary consent form to access the scale forms.

Data Collection Tools

The "Personal Information Form" created by the researchers was used to determine the distribution of the personal information of the participants who participated in the study. The form includes 9 questions such as gender, age, and favorite team. In order to obtain the opinions of the participants on the causes of violence in sports, the "Basics of Violence in Sports Scale" developed by Reyhan (2017) within the scope of his doctoral thesis and published by Reyhan et al. (2020) was used. The scale is a self-report scale and has 25 items (e.g. media evaluations before matches lead fans to violence) and a 5-factor structure. Responses to the scale are evaluated on a 5-point Likert-type scale. Items 1-2-3-4-5 and 6 constitute the sub-dimension of "violence caused by sports media", items 7-8-9-10- and 11 constitute the sub-dimension of "violence caused by referee decisions", items 12-13-14- and 15 constitute the sub-dimension of "violence caused by coaches and technical directors", items 16-17-18-19-20 and 21 constitute the sub-dimension of "violence caused by fans and cheerleaders" and items 22-23-24- and 25 constitute the sub-dimension of "violence caused by athlete behavior".

Data Analysis

After the data obtained in the study were entered into the Excel program via Google Form, the participants who provided incomplete information were removed. The data organized in the Excel program were transferred to the SPSS 26 package program and the relevant statistical procedures were performed. The internal consistency coefficient was not calculated for the data collection tool ($\alpha=.809$; $N=25$). The distribution of the data was determined by examining kurtosis and skewness values. In addition to descriptive statistical methods, one-way analysis of variance test, Pearson correlation analysis and independent sample t test were used in the study.

FINDINGS

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics Results for The Data Collection Tool

Causes of Violence in Sports	N	Mean	Std. D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Media-Induced Violence	290	3,04	,626	-,280	,364
Violence Arising from Arbitral Awards	290	3,29	,828	-,044	-,095
Violence by Coaches and Technical Directors	290	2,59	,894	,108	-,457
Violence by Fans and Cheerleaders	290	2,80	,579	-,172	1,091
Violence Caused by Athlete Behavior	290	2,50	,777	,066	-,162

According to the results of the analysis, the highest average score the participants received from the scale of the bases of violence in sports was in the sub-dimension of "violence caused by referee decisions", while the lowest average score was in the sub-dimension of "violence caused by athlete behavior". In addition, when the kurtosis and skewness values are analyzed, it is understood that the data do not show an excessive deviation from normal.

Table 2. Participants' Frequency of Going to The Match According to Their Gender

	Match Attendance Frequency			
	I go to home soccer matches	As the Team Succeeds I'll go	As Time Allows I'll go	I go to every matches
Male	7,5% (N=10)	9,0% (N=12)	80,5% (N=107)	3,0% (N=4)
Woman	3,2% (N=5)	8,9% (N=14)	85,4% (N=107)	2,5% (N=4)
Total	5,2% (N=15)	9,0% (N=26)	83,1% (N=241)	2,8% (N=8)

According to the results of the analysis, 7.5% of the male participants stated that they went to home matches, 9.0% stated that they went to home matches when the team was successful, 80.5% stated that they went to home matches when they had time and 3.0% stated that they went to every match. Among the female participants, 3.2% stated that they went to home matches, 8.9% stated that they went to home matches when the team was successful, 85.4% stated that they went to home matches when they had time and 2.5% stated that they went to every match.

Table 3. Correlation Analysis Results for Age and Violence in Sports

1-Age	1	2	3	4	5	6
2-Media-Induced Violence	-0,039	1				
3-Violence Arising from Referee Decisions	-0,04	,474**	1			
4-Violence Caused by Coaches and Technical Directors	-0,017	,334**	,517**	1		
5-Violence by Fans and Cheerleaders	0,013	,169**	,258**	,355**	1	
6-Violence Caused by Athlete Behavior	-0,114	,308**	,386**	,468**	,281**	1

*p<0.05 *P<0.01 N=290

Pearson Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between the participants' ages and their views on the bases of violence in sports. According to the results of the analysis, significant positive relationships were found between the ages of the participants and their views on the basics of violence in sports.

Table 4. Independent Sample T Test Analysis Results on Gender and Violence in Sports

Fundamentals of Violence in Sport	Gender	N	Mean	Std. D.	t	p
Media-Induced Violence	Male	133	3,210	0,579	4,425	0,000
	Woman	157	2,896	0,629		
Violence Arising from Arbitral Awards	Male	133	3,449	0,742	3,016	0,003
	Woman	157	3,163	0,875		
Violence by Coaches and Technical Directors	Male	133	2,548	0,833	-0,767	0,444
	Woman	157	2,629	0,945		
Violence by Fans and Cheerleaders	Male	133	2,886	0,539	2,123	0,035
	Woman	157	2,743	0,605		
Violence Caused by Athlete Behavior	Male	133	2,580	0,777	1,459	0,146
	Woman	157	2,447	0,773		

Independent sample t test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference between the participants' views on the bases of violence in sports according to their gender. According to the results of the analysis, men's sub-dimension scores of violence caused by media, violence caused by referee decisions and violence caused by fans and cheerleaders are significantly higher than women. The sub-dimension scores of violence caused by coaches and technical directors and violence caused by athlete behavior of female and male participants did not show a significant difference in terms of gender.

Table 5. Independent Sample T Test Analysis Results on Smoking and Violence in Sports

Fundamentals of Violence in Sport	Do you smoke?	N	Mean	Std. D.	t	p
Media-Induced Violence	Yes	91	3,031	0,692	-0,158	0,875
	No	199	3,044	0,595		
Violence Arising from Arbitral Awards	Yes	91	3,402	0,805	1,521	0,130
	No	199	3,245	0,835		
Violence by Coaches and Technical Directors	Yes	91	2,596	0,844	0,052	0,959
	No	199	2,590	0,919		
Violence by Fans and Cheerleaders	Yes	91	2,782	0,616	-0,510	0,611
	No	199	2,820	0,563		
Violence Caused by Athlete Behavior	Yes	91	2,587	0,777	1,175	0,242
	No	199	2,472	0,775		

Independent sample t test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of smoking. According to the results of the analysis, there was no significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of smoking.

Table 6. Independent Sample T Test Analysis Results on Alcohol Use and Violence in Sports

Fundamentals of Violence in Sport	Do you drink alcohol?	N	Mean	Std. D.	t	p
Media-Induced Violence	Yes	58	3,005	0,706	-0,427	0,640
	No	232	3,048	0,606		
Violence Arising from Arbitral Awards	Yes	58	3,355	0,806	-0,636	0,534
	No	232	3,279	0,834		
Violence by Coaches and Technical Directors	Yes	58	2,508	0,995	-0,733	0,427
	No	232	2,613	0,869		
Violence by Fans and Cheerleaders	Yes	58	2,701	0,598	-1,541	0,127
	No	232	2,835	0,573		
Violence Caused by Athlete Behavior	Yes	58	2,594	0,923	0,825	0,412
	No	232	2,487	0,736		

Independent sample t test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of alcohol use. According to the results of the analysis, there was no significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of alcohol use.

Table 7. Independent Sample T Test Analysis Results on Licensed Sports Experience and Violence in Sports

Fundamentals of Violence in Sport	Did you play sports under license?	N	Mean	Std. D.	t	p
Media-Induced Violence	Yes	131	3,103	0,693	1,523	0,129
	No	159	2,988	0,561		
Violence Arising from Arbitral Awards	Yes	131	3,311	0,907	-0,311	0,756
	No	159	3,280	0,759		
Violence by Coaches and Technical Directors	Yes	131	2,532	0,996	-1,012	0,313
	No	159	2,641	0,801		
Violence by Fans and Cheerleaders	Yes	131	2,787	0,611	-0,556	0,579
	No	159	2,826	0,553		
Violence Caused by Athlete Behavior	Yes	131	2,511	0,850	0,055	0,956
	No	159	2,506	0,713		

An independent sample t-test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of their licensed sports experience. According to the results of the analysis, there was no significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of their licensed sports experience.

Table 8. One-Way Analysis of Variance Test Results on Frequency of Going to The Match and Violence in Sports

Fundamentals of Violence in Sport	Match Attendance Frequency	N	Mean	Std. D.	F	p
Media-Induced Violence	I go to home soccer matches	15	2,755	0,823	1,768	0,153
	As the Team Succeeds I'll go	26	3,044	0,688		
	As Time Allows I'll go	241	3,067	0,592		
	I go to every matches	8	2,750	0,890		
	<i>Total</i>	290	3,040	0,626		
Violence Arising from Arbitral Awards	I go to home soccer matches	15	3,426	0,894	0,152	0,928
	As the Team Succeeds I'll go	26	3,323	0,856		
	As Time Allows I'll go	241	3,283	0,813		
	I go to every matches	8	3,300	1,166		
	<i>Total</i>	290	3,294	0,828		
Violence by Coaches and Technical Directors	I go to home soccer matches	15	2,416	0,765	0,204	0,894
	As the Team Succeeds I'll go	26	2,615	1,160		
	As Time Allows I'll go	241	2,600	0,874		
	I go to every matches	8	2,593	0,895		
	<i>Total</i>	290	2,592	0,894		
Violence by Fans and Cheerleaders	I go to home soccer matches	15	2,766	0,416	0,197	0,899
	As the Team Succeeds I'll go	26	2,820	0,539		
	As Time Allows I'll go	241	2,814	0,601		
	I go to every matches	8	2,666	0,251		
	<i>Total</i>	290	2,808	0,579		
Violence Caused by Athlete Behavior	I go to home soccer matches	15	2,133	0,766	1,746	0,158
	As the Team Succeeds I'll go	26	2,576	0,780		
	As Time Allows I'll go	241	2,513	0,777		
	I go to every matches	8	2,843	0,640		
	<i>Total</i>	290	2,508	0,777		

One-way analysis of variance test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in the participants' views on the bases of violence in sports according to the frequency of going to the match at the stadium. According to the results of the analysis, no significant difference was found in the participants' views on the basics of violence in sports according to the frequency of attending the match at the stadium.

Table 9. Independent Sample T Test Analysis Results on Membership to A Fan Group and Violence in Sports

Fundamentals of Violence in Sport	Are you a fan of any team?	N	Mean	Std. D.	t	p
Media-Induced Violence	Yes	253	3,023	0,623	-1,145	0,258
	No	37	3,153	0,644		
Violence Arising from Arbitral Awards	Yes	253	3,235	0,786	-2,704	0,010
	No	37	3,697	0,994		
Violence by Coaches and Technical Directors	Yes	253	2,565	0,875	-1,207	0,234
	No	37	2,777	1,013		
Violence by Fans and Cheerleaders	Yes	253	2,809	0,568	0,023	0,982
	No	37	2,806	0,663		
Violence Caused by Athlete Behavior	Yes	253	2,462	0,735	-2,180	0,035
	No	37	2,824	0,969		

The scores of the fan group members were found to be significantly higher in the sub-dimensions of violence caused by referee decisions and violence caused by athlete behavior. There was no significant difference in terms of violence caused by media, violence caused by coaches and technical directors, violence caused by fans and cheerleaders.

Table 10. Independent Sample T-Test Analysis Results on Involvement in Any Stadium Incident and Violence in Sports

Fundamentals of Violence in Sport	Were you involved in any stadium incidents?	N	Mean	Std. D.	t	p
Media-Induced Violence	No	274	3,0268	0,62271	-1,435	0,170
	Yes	16	3,2708	0,66353		
Violence Arising from Arbitral Awards	No	274	3,2825	0,81671	-0,842	0,412
	Yes	16	3,5000	1,01456		
Violence by Coaches and Technical Directors	No	274	2,5821	0,88724	-0,695	0,497
	Yes	16	2,7656	1,03468		
Violence by Fans and Cheerleaders	No	274	2,8066	0,56963	-0,193	0,849
	Yes	16	2,8438	0,75638		
Violence Caused by Athlete Behavior	No	274	2,5018	0,76226	-0,475	0,641
	Yes	16	2,6250	1,02062		

Independent sample t-test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of having been involved in any violent incident. According to the results of the analysis, no significant difference was found in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of having been involved in any violent incident.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

According to the results of our study to examine the tendencies of university students towards violence and hooliganism in sports, Pearson Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between the age of the participants and their views on the basics of violence in sports. According to the results of the analysis, significant positive relationships were found between the ages of the participants and their views on the basics of violence in sports. In a study conducted by Özen, Eygü and Kababaş (2013) on university students' perceptions of violence and aggression in sports, it is stated that the statements of the fans that they say bad words after the referees' decisions against the team are related to the age of the individuals participating in the study. In the same study, to the question of how cheerleaders affect the spectators, it was determined that the statements that the cheerleaders direct the fans to organized, positive cheering and violence are related to the age of the participants. It is stated that the statements of booing and whistling to the question of what kind of cheers do you participate in during the competition are related to the age of the participants. In the study conducted by Çağlayan and Fişekçioğlu (2004) on football spectators, it is stated that as the age level of the spectators decreases, the probability of involvement in incidents increases. In the study conducted by Yalçın Ekinçi & Ayhan (2021), significant differences were found in violence tendency according to various variables. Koçer (2012) examined the hooliganism and violence tendencies of fans who are members of football associations. In his study, it is seen that fans younger than 18 years of age have more violence and aggression tendencies than those between 18-24 years of age, the effect of team defeat on fans younger than 18 years of age is

more than those between 18-24 years of age, fans younger than 18 years of age support their teams more than those aged 25 and over, and as their age decreases, they are more provoked by the events and phenomena around them. In the study conducted by Gümüşgül (2016) investigating the effect of participation in leisure time activities on the prevention of violence, hooliganism and aggressive behaviors in football spectators, the level of aggression and violence in sports differs significantly depending on age. In the study by Çakto and Akın (2023), in which the violence tendencies of the spectators participating in the 2022 FIFA World Cup were examined, a statistically significant difference was found between the age variable and the tendency to violence. In the same study, it is emphasized that the tendency to violence decreases with advancing age.

Independent sample t test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference between the participants' views on the bases of violence in sports according to their gender. According to the results of the analysis, men's sub-dimension scores of violence caused by media, violence caused by referee decisions and violence caused by fans and cheerleaders are significantly higher than women. The sub-dimension scores of violence caused by coaches and technical directors and violence caused by athlete behavior of female and male participants did not show a significant difference in terms of gender. Karademir et al. (2021) conducted a study to examine the violence tendencies of taekwondo athletes and found that there was no statistically significant difference in the violence tendency levels of taekwondo athletes depending on the gender variable. In the study conducted by Koçer (2012), it is seen that the aggression and violence tendencies of female fans, the effects caused by the loss of the team, the behaviors and attitudes related to supporting the team, and being quickly affected by the events and being provoked are lower than men. It was determined that the hooliganism and violence tendencies of these female fans were quite low compared to men. In the study conducted by Gümüşgül (2016) in which the effect of participation in leisure time activities on the prevention of violence, hooliganism and aggressive behaviors in football spectators was investigated, it was determined that there was a significant difference between demographic characteristics such as age, marital status, average monthly income and age and the levels of aggression and violence in sports. In their study, Kuru and Var (2009) found significant relationships between gender and views on the bases of violence in sports. In general, when the literature is examined, it is observed that male participants are more aggressive than female participants.

Independent sample t test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of smoking. According to the results of the analysis, there was no significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports

in terms of smoking. In contrast to our study, İftar (2016) found that the violence attitude scores of smoking students were higher than those of non-smoking students in the comparisons made on substance use of university students, and the difference was found to be significant. In the correlation analysis conducted by Altuner, et al. (2009), a positive correlation was found between substance use and being exposed to physical violence, committing physical violence and showing various violent behaviors. Again, Bebiş, Coşkun, and Açıkel (2014) found that smoking and use of any substance harmful to health were higher in students with very high violence tendency. Karakaya (2008), in his study conducted in Industrial Vocational High Schools, determined that students who smoke cigarettes adopt violence more.

Independent sample t test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of alcohol use. According to the results of the analysis, no significant difference was found in terms of alcohol use in the participants' views on violence in sports. In the study conducted by İftar (2016), although the attitude scores of students who used alcohol were higher than the attitude scores of students who did not use alcohol, there was no statistically significant difference between them in the analysis. While these findings support our study, Gümüştül (2016) found a statistically significant difference in the behavioral level aggression sub-dimension, cognitive level aggression sub-dimension and affective level aggression sub-dimension according to alcohol use. In the study conducted by Şanlı (2014) on the examination of the aggression levels of the spectators during football matches, it is seen that there is a significant difference between the aggression level of the spectators and whether or not they use alcohol while going to watch the match. When the rank averages are taken into consideration, it is understood that those who use alcohol while going to watch a match have higher levels of aggression than those who do not. This finding indicates that alcohol use is effective in increasing the level of aggression. Tutkun, et al. (2012) found high rates of alcohol use among fans. He also found that they have a tendency towards aggression and violence. The mental state, beliefs, expectations and value judgments of individuals who drink alcohol play an important role in the emergence of aggression (Köknel, 1997). According to Krech, Crutchfield & Livson (1974), when an individual encounters a problem and his/her physiological state changes (intoxication), the behavior of the individual changes when some dynamic factors are activated in the process. Finally, Orhan (2007), in his study on sports security in order to prevent violence and disorder in sports, states that while some countries establish a link between alcohol and drug consumption and spectator violence, according to some countries, alcohol and drug consumption does not have a triggering effect on spectator violence.

An independent sample t-test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of their licensed sports experience. According to the results of the analysis, there was no significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of their licensed sports experience. In the study conducted by Aydın, et al. (2015) with students continuing their education in secondary school, it was seen that there was no significant difference in the violence tendencies of the students depending on the variables of gender and doing sports. Again, Karademir, Kayabaşı and Vural (2019) supported these findings with the results of their study.

One-way analysis of variance test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in the participants' views on the bases of violence in sports according to the frequency of attending matches at the stadium. According to the results of the analysis, no significant difference was found in the participants' views on the bases of violence in sports according to the frequency of attending matches at the stadium. When the related literature was examined, Yıldız (2014) found in his study on the violent behavior of football fans that there is no statistically significant difference between the calm behaviors scale, the anger symptoms scale score of individuals and the aggressive behaviors scale score of individuals between the status of individuals watching football matches in the stadium. However, it was found that individuals who watched the matches in the stadium had higher levels of aggressive behaviors than individuals who did not watch the matches. In their study, Pepe (2012) states that fans see the stadium as a place to relieve stress and therefore, fans who watch matches in the stadium are more involved in violent incidents. Polat and Sönmez (2016) also supported these findings with their research results.

According to the results of our study to examine the violence and hooliganism tendencies of university students in sports, the scores of the fan group members were found to be significantly higher in the sub-dimensions of violence caused by referee decisions and violence caused by athlete behavior. There was no significant difference in terms of violence caused by media, violence caused by coaches and technical directors, violence caused by fans and cheerleaders. In the literature researches followed, studies similar to our study were found. Reyhan and Müniroğlu (2017) found significant relationships between being a member of any fan group and their views on the basis of violence in sports. Again, the studies conducted by Koçer (2012) and Polat and Sönmezoğlu (2016) support our study. Yıldız (2014) stated that 245 (89.1%) of the individuals participating in his study were not members of the club they were a fan of, while 30 (10.9%) were members of the club they were a fan of. Of these members, 261 (94.9%) have not damaged the seats, doors, etc. in the stadium before and 14 (5.1%) have damaged the seats, doors, etc. in the stadium before. In the study, there was a significant difference between the

scores of the aggressive behaviors scale, reckless reactions scale and trait anger scale and the status of purchasing the products of the club they are supporters of.

Independent sample t-test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of having been involved in any violent incident. According to the results of the analysis, no significant difference was found in the participants' views on violence in sports in terms of their involvement in any violent incident. Gümüşgül (2016) examined whether the spectators in his study were involved in any stadium incident before, and 20.8% (N=547) of the participants in the study were involved in any stadium incident before, while 79.2% (N=2077) stated that they were not involved in any stadium incident. Abdal-Haqq (2012) identifies a number of factors that encourage violence in sports. These include cues given by players, cheerleaders, spectators and coaches. In sports environments, spectators gain social identity through their teams. They perceive rival teams as enemies by creating a bond between coaches, fans and players that creates group unity. The perception of other teams as enemies encourages hostility. He states that hostility includes supporters, minorities, geographical regions and other social classes. In Yıldız's (2014) study, there is no statistically significant difference in terms of the calm behaviors scale score of individuals between whether the individuals fought verbally or physically with their friends during their school life. There is a statistically significant difference in terms of passive aggressive scale score between whether individuals verbally or physically fought with their friends during school life. It was found that individuals who fought verbally or physically with their friends during school life had higher levels of anger symptoms than individuals who did not fight. It was found that individuals who fought verbally or physically with their friends during their school life had higher levels of aggressive behaviors compared to individuals who did not fight. Again, 240 (87.3%) of the individuals were not involved in any violent incidents in or around stadiums, while 35 (12.7%) were involved in any violent incidents in or around stadiums. It is stated that 246 (89.5%) of the individuals have not been detained by the police before for any crime, while 29 (10.5%) have been detained by the police before for any crime. With the results obtained in our study; while there were significant differences in the parameters of the participants' age, gender and membership to any fan group, there were no significant differences in the parameters of smoking, alcohol use, licensed sports experience and frequency of going to the match. In addition, when the results of the questionnaire were examined, it was seen that the highest average score the participants received from the scale of the bases of violence in sports was in the sub-dimension of "violence caused by referee decisions", followed by the sub-dimensions of "violence caused by the media", "violence caused by fans and cheerleaders" and "violence caused by coaches and technical directors"

respectively. As a result, when the tendencies of university students towards violence and hooliganism in sports were analyzed, it was seen that male students had higher scores than female students. It was observed that the participants showed tendency to violence mostly due to referee decisions and media.

Recommendations

According to the results, the following suggestions are made;

- In the context of directing fans to violence, the content of the news and programs broadcast by broadcasting institutions and the press can be controlled and their content can be limited if necessary.
- Efforts can be made to ensure that team managers, coaches and football players who give statements to media organs and the press use a better language.
- Legal regulations that can prevent fan violence in football can be reviewed and deterrence can be increased.

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